

Trends in Business Analytics: 2018 and beyond

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ABSTRACT

Literature dictates that trends in business analytics in the coming future will be dominated by Business Intelligence, Automation, IoT (Internet of Things), Artificial Intelligence, BlockChain, etc. Despite the influx of new technologies, there is a constant need to reinvent and modernise business analytics trends in the present day to stay relevant. This review echoes the importance of data analytics and artificial intelligence as two primary trends. All the other movements like Automation, BI, BlockChain, and IoT seem to emerge from these two crucial elements. For future success, the digital platform models with a distinct organisational shift towards teamwork and customer-centric approaches will be the new trend in conducting business.

KEYWORDS: Business analytics, Artificial Intelligence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Business data is the backbone of the insight-driven decision-making process, which helps organisations to stay ahead of the curve. Trends in business analytics range from Business Intelligence (BI); Cloud BI; Automation; Artificial Intelligence; Predictive Analysis; NLP (Natural Language Processing); Data protection; Blockchain etc. and with the influx of new technologies, there is a constant need to reinvent and modernise the trends of Business analytics in the present day to stay relevant.

Trends in business analytics are based on two primaries, i.e. analytics and artificial intelligence (Davenport and Harris, 2017). From 2016 onwards, the advent of adoption of Artificial Intelligence has increased globally from 20-30% (Deloitte, 2017). Artificial intelligence is embedded with automated cognitive technologies "Robotic process automation" for digital tasks (Davenport and Kirby, 2016). Historically, data analytics had three stages (Davenport, 2013): descriptive statistics, data management, and analysis. It was mostly for internal decision making and had barely any predictive capabilities.

This trend shifted to the next stage of 'Big Data', that employed data management platform like 'Hadoop' used by Google, Facebook, LinkedIn, etc. and the trend was now more for data-driven products using the principles of machine learning and not just internal decision-making process which dominated the business intelligence industry in the earlier years. In the present stage, data analytics and modelling have become an organisational culture where the companies are invested in expertise and transforming business with the help of data that is specifically created using machine learning models. They have evolved into data products (Davenport and Pati, 2012).

Thus, data analytics has moved beyond its descriptive capabilities into prescriptive capabilities (read- Artificial Intelligence) to enhance establishments of education; healthcare; governance; public transport system; waste management, etc. therefore, this review is going to delve

into the trends in business analytics ranging from analytics to data security to data implementation, from the current date into 2018 and beyond.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The various trends in business analytics that are likely to dominate 2018 and beyond are as follows:

2.1 Business Intelligence (BI)

The importance of unstructured data like emails; blogs; internet-based posts on Facebook; texts; images, audio, etc., along with structured data, has been the mainstay of Business Intelligence (BI) activity useful for operational business decision making (Sicular and Gartner, 2013).

Business intelligence is based on probing and recording information from business analytics, primarily features of -what had happened in the past, now, using big data techniques to source information for action to be taken in the future. This has been achieved by using platforms like Apache project and Hadoop (White, 2012), which efficiently handle data at a low cost.

2.2 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Kok *et al.* (2009) have elucidated the concept of artificial intelligence as "creating intelligent computers". The computers are taught artificial intelligence using the four features, i.e. NLP- to learn the language such as English, Knowledge representation- to store the knowledge in its system, Automation-it should be able to reason based on stirred knowledge and Machine learning- and learn from its environment. In the coming years, an intelligent mesh of things, people, processes, places, devices, services, and the content will become increasingly digitalised, and artificial intelligence will play an essential role in these critical initiatives like speech recognition; computer vision; self-driving cars; intelligent cities; risk management, etc. (Cearley *et al.*, 2017).

AI technology can boost decision making and help develop business models based on expert systems like regression models, decision trees, neural networks, advanced algorithms with supervised and unsupervised reinforcement learning techniques, etc. It also uses sophisticated hardware and big data to feed the machine learning technology. As AI techniques and processes are increasing, a team of data scientists need to understand and implement solutions and application developers for interface, process, and services flow. The various trends in AI are tabulated as follows (Cearley *et al.*, 2017):

3. TRENDS IN AI

3.1 AI-powered Intelligent Apps and Analytics

Acts as a VCA (virtual customer assistant); enhances workers' performance, sales, and marketing of the firm, security issues, etc.

3.2 Intelligent Things

Robots – in healthcare, aviation, consumer items, etc.

3.3 Digital Twins

CAD models; Statistical models; Analytical simulation models, for example, creating smart cities, etc.

3.4 Edge Computing

For example, Microsoft 365

3.5 Conversational Platforms

Amazon's Alexa; Google assistant; Apple's Siri; Chatbots etc.

3.6 Immersive experience

Augmented / Virtual reality

3.7 Blockchain

For example, Banking, Healthcare, Supply chain

3.8 Event-Driven Model

Example: Salesforce, SAP, etc.

3.9 Continuous Adaptive Risk and Trust (CARTA)

Prevention of cyber attacks

3.10 Automation

Sauter *et al.* (2011) explained automation as the "flow of information between sensors, controllers and actuators". The newest trends in automation are the Internet of Things (IoT), tactile internet, and CPS. This technology has found a place in the oil and gas industry, with the help of data recording sensors to explore, drill, production operations for petrochemicals; shipping; transportation, and occupational safety (Mohammadpoor and Torabi, 2018). But the challenges faced by this industry are the cost associated with: storage, data recording, and interpretation of results; data ownership problems; and having an interdisciplinary team also consisting of computer scientists to define and solve the data-driven concerns.

3.11 Internet of Things (IoT)

The internet of things hypothesises that everyday articles can be fortified with sensing, identifying, processing, and networking capabilities and are linked to the internet to achieve some objective (Whitmore *et al.*, 2015). For example, IoT helps integrate smart objects into the internet and provide different kinds of services like RFID (radio frequency identification technology), e-health, Smart Grids, smart homes, and maritime industries (Whitmore *et al.*, 2013). It can also be used for societal impact based on three principles: data and its substructure, data interpretation techniques, and its applications. The applications range from EHR (electronic healthcare records); Lifestyle Management; Critical infrastructure, for example, chemical sector; dams; defence; food and agriculture, emergency services etc.(PPD-21, 2017). IoT uses cloud computing, wireless technology, real-time analytics, machine learning, embedded systems sensors, automation, etc. Trends of IoT are predicted to add 12-15 trillion dollars to the GDP from 2012-2032 (Saha *et al.* 2017 and Gupta *et al.*, 2018).

3.12 Blockchain

It is one of the leading technologies for 2018 and beyond, especially in safe peer-to-peer money transactions, commodity transactions, insurance, and financial sector, in sustainable logistics and supply chain management. Its data are stored in decentralised cloud storage solutions. Blockchain is a distributed book ledger with many applications, for example, IBM, Oracle SAP, etc. (Flureedb, 2017 & McConaghy *et al.*, 2016) are essential forerunners that use this technology. It exchanges data for financial payments, shipments, etc. Every action is stored as a block distributed over many nodes of computers making the system transparent, especially in supply chain and logistics, and tracking the physical movement of goods is more accessible. Therefore this technology plays a vital role in decision making and is very satisfying to the customers (Efthymiou *et al.*, 2013).

3.13 Organisational Change and Development

With rapidly evolving digital technology, the future of organisations and the skills required are also facing changes to be successful in the future, and they are dependent on three main criteria: Big Data, organisational changes in the form of teamwork, shifting geographical and ethnic demographics, and values. The traditional Organisation Development models will be more digitalised Platform models, i.e. customer-centric adaptive service approach (Church and Burke, 2017).

4. CONCLUSION

This review provides a synopsis of the future trends of business analytics. This review echoes the importance of data analytics and artificial intelligence as two primary trends. All the other movements like Automation, BI, BlockChain, and IoT seem to emerge from these two crucial elements. For future success, the digital platform models with a distinct organisational shift towards teamwork and customer-centric approaches will be the new trend in conducting business.

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